

PHILOSOPHICAL ANALYSIS OF FAMILY PROBLEMS

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Annotation: Family ethno-traditions cannot be considered separately from people's culture, lifestyle, thinking and dreams. There is no separate family ethno-tradition, it is always analyzed through the synthesis of national culture and values.

Keywords: Man, family, institution of marriage, strength of the family, personnel, national and spiritual values, transformation of values.

Main part

Philosophical analysis of family problems shows that family ties have not always served as a decisive basis for creating a family. The concept of "family" originally included not only father, mother and children. A family is defined as the entire household, including people who live under the same roof or are under the authority of one person. In addition to the family itself, many relatives, servants, slaves and even dogs were included here. Such a family was considered a group of people united for the purpose of effective social regulation or management. History shows that the composition of the family group depends on this strong social system and economic way of life in general.

Regarding the issue of the beginning of family history, the Swiss historian I. Yes. In his 1861 work, *The Right of Motherhood*, Bachofen put forward the following arguments:

- 1) originally, people had unlimited sex, defined by the word "heterism";
- 2) such a relationship excludes any possibility of determining the exactness of the father, for this reason the origin of the descendants is determined only by the female line, by the right of motherhood;

3) because of this, women, as mothers, received the highest, only trust, respect and respect in front of the younger generation, that is, the complete domination of women was ensured;

4) the transition of a woman to monogamy, which belongs to only one man, led to the violation of the most ancient rules, that is, in fact, it led to the violation of the primitive right of other men to this woman ¹.

However, at this point, it is appropriate to raise some objections to these ideas put forward by Bachofen, in which the scientist advocated and responded to the issue of women's rights. He thinks that transition to monogamous family is a violation of primitive rights. There is also a second side to the issue, which is the issue of determining the paternity of the child. The only solution to this problem is through a monogamous family.

Also, the family issue was discussed in 1871 by the American historian and ethnographer L. Studied by Morgan, he provided new and largely decisive material. He tried to determine the system of periodization of the life of American Indians, the development of the family and human society in general. It distinguishes the development evolution of mankind from "the lowest stage of savagery to the stage of civilization".

Based on his periodization system, Morgan divides the formation of the family into several stages. These are according to the scientist:

1. Irregular marriage, i.e. marriage between brothers and sisters (marriage based on promiscuity).
2. Polygamy
3. Polygamy
4. A family consisting of one man and one woman.

Thus, the starting point of studying the family goes back to a long history. Family relations L. The method proposed by Morgan is the beginning of human history, the first form of historical development. Without studying the family as a historical category, it is impossible to understand its social essence. Modern science has fully

¹ Bachofen J.S. Myth, Religion and Mother Right. - New Jersey, 1967. - 309 p.
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confirmed this. The family phenomenon was analyzed in the general context of social development in classical social philosophy and family relations. Only in the 20th century, the issue of studying the family became an issue of a separate science.

The problem of family stability and strength cannot be ignored without scientific analysis and without studying its historical foundations. Because, knowledge about any thing and event is formed through a deep analysis of the appearance of that thing, the causes of the occurrence of the event. Inculcation of the phenomenon of family strength in the minds of young people is done by explaining the formation of things and events (family), its content and social importance in society. I.A. Karimov in his work "High spirituality - indomitable power" emphasized that the role and influence of the family is incomparable in the formation and promotion of the unique spirituality of any nation. "Truly, the first concepts of life in a person, worldview, virgin feelings, the first buds of spirituality begin to appear, first of all, they are formed under the influence of the family environment"².

The most important task of the family is to pass on traditions and values to the next generation, which ensures social continuity in society. Family connects the past with the future through the present. For this reason, a person should look at his life not only today, but as a bridge connecting the past and the future. Only then, people value family, family stability, and family relations as value, and in the form of transformation of values, they are passed on to the next generation, and they feel that there is a whole chain of life behind them.

The basis of the social organism is the division of labor, which ensures social cohesion, because it develops socially al instinct, each family feels a common dependence and participates in the social cooperation of labor. The family obeys the social hierarchy and the immutable law of subordination: the woman must obey the man in it, and the younger ones must obey the elders. The strength of the family largely depends on the relations of its members, the place of each member in the family, the respect of the younger ones for the older ones, respect for values in general and their

² I.A.Karimov "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch". Toshkent. Ma'naviyat. 2008. 55-6er
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transmission to the next generations.

The stronger the family, the stronger and more developed the society. For this reason, it is no coincidence that since 1994, the General Assembly of the United Nations decided to celebrate May 15 every year as "International Family Day", and the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" also focused on the issue of family. For example, Article 16 of the "Universal Declaration of Human Rights" states: "Men and women of full age have the right to marry and start a family without any restrictions depending on their race, nationality and religion." They enjoy the same rights when they get married, while they are married, and when the marriage is annulled. The fact that the issue of the family and its sovereignty is expressed in international documents shows the importance of this social institution at the international level. Therefore, every young generation living in our country should deeply understand the importance of family, evaluate it as a value, and form a strong concept of family in their minds.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above-mentioned considerations in this part of the work.

In Islamic teachings, family, marriage and couple relations are given a lot of attention. This issue has been raised to the level of fard and sunnah, and it is given a special place in the Holy Qur'an and Hadith Sharifs in separate chapters and verses and in the advice of the Prophet. Based on this, Imam Ghazali states that wives have many rights to their husbands. First of all, their physical weakness as a gender, their spiritual attractiveness, and good health require special consideration and mercy, to endure their sufferings and to forgive some of their sins.

The same idea is expressed in the holy book of Islam, the Holy Qur'an: "O believers, it is not lawful for you to inherit wives by force. Do not crush them in order to get some of your dowry, unless they have committed an open debauchery. Treat them well. Be patient even if you hate them, Allah may have done many good things in what you hate.

Also, Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), as a great scientist, tried to reveal the scientific essence of all phenomena. Alloma emphasized the role of the family in matters of moral

education. The issue of family and family relations is described in his work "Tadbiri Manzil" in a unique way.

In the works of philosophers of antiquity, scholars of the Middle Ages, as well as in the modern era, many researchers and scientists attached special importance to the institution of the family, and in their works and socio-ethnological views, they advocated the idea that the nature of social relations and the nature of its manifestation should be sought on the basis of family relations.

In the institutional formation of the family, the sexual, moral and property relations between men and women play a decisive role. These relations are formed and passed in a certain cultural, ethnic and social environment. From this point of view, the formation of the family as an institution is a gradual product of these relations. Ethnological characteristics give it nationality, locality or universality, universality, national characteristics become national values as an integral attribute of historical and cultural development.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE

1. Aristotle. Sochinenia. T.4.–Moscow: Misli, 1983. P.377;
2. See: Nishonova O. The aesthetic essence of Uzbek ethnoculture. - Tashkent: Fan, 2013. 127-129 b;
3. See: Bacon F. Sochinenia v dvux tomax. T.2.--Moscow: Mysl, 1972. P.367;
4. Semenov Yu.I. Proishkhojdenie braka i semi. - M.: Nauka, 1974;
5. Mid M. Kultura i mir detstva. Izbrannye proizvedeniya. - M.: Gl. ed. Vostoch. literature, 1988;
6. Weninger O. Pol i character. – Rostov-on-Don, Phoenix, 1998;
7. Semya 1 2. Kniga dlya chteniya. - M.: Politizdat, 1991;
8. Ubaidullaeva R.A. Semya v Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: 2012
9. Barth F. Ethnic Groups and Boundaries. Introduction Boston. 1969;
10. Bromley Yu.V. Essay theory of ethnos. - Moscow: Nauka, 1983;